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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Lung cancer remains the most commonly diagnosed cancer and the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide and in our country. Despite advances in early detection and treatment, the disease can exhibit unpredictable behavior.

Case Presentation: In this report, we present a rare case of a patient diagnosed with Stage 1 lung cancer, who developed distant organ metastasis several years after initial treatment and presumed remission.

Discussion: The late recurrence of metastatic disease, in the absence of earlier clinical or radiologic signs, underscores the importance of long-term follow-up even in early-stage lung cancer cases. This case also raises questions regarding the underlying genetic and molecular mechanisms that may contribute to such delayed progression.

Conclusion: Our findings highlight the complexity of lung cancer biology and the potential limitations of current staging and surveillance protocols.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Lung cancer, early stage, screening program

INTRODUCTION

In our case, a lung cancer detected at an early stage presented with distant organ metastasis years later. This case once again demonstrates how lung cancer can be both genetically and a hidden threat. Lung cancer remains the most commonly diagnosed malignancy and the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide and in our country (ESMO, 2025). It is broadly classified into two major histological subtypes: small cell lung cancer (SCLC) and non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), the latter accounting for approximately 85% of all cases. Among NSCLC subtypes, adenocarcinoma has become the most prevalent form, particularly among non-smokers and in regions such as ours (Cangir et al., 2022; Kızıllırmak et al., 2023). Despite advances in early detection and treatment modalities, lung cancer continues to pose significant clinical challenges due to its potential for aggressive behavior, even when diagnosed at an early stage. While Stage 1 lung cancer is typically associated with a favorable prognosis following curative treatment, unpredictable clinical courses, such as late-onset distant metastasis, may still occur. In this case report, we present a patient initially diagnosed with Stage 1 lung adenocarcinoma who later developed distant organ metastasis after several years of apparent remission. This case underscores the need for a deeper understanding of tumor biology, including mechanisms of dormancy, micro-metastasis, and late recurrence. It highlights that lung cancer, even when seemingly localized, can harbor latent threats that necessitate long-term vigilance and individualized follow-up strategies.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 57-year-old male presented to the pulmonology outpatient clinic in February 2022 with complaints of cough and sputum production. On physical examination, diminished breath sounds were noted. A chest X-ray revealed a nodular lesion in the right lower lobe, and thoracic CT confirmed a 2 cm solid mass (Image 1).

Image 1

Thoracic CT, a 2 cm solid nodular lesion in the right lower lobe, Feb 2022

Initial Diagnosis and Treatment: For staging, PET-CT was performed, and no evidence of metastasis was found. The patient was referred to thoracic surgery with a preliminary diagnosis of Stage I non-small cell lung cancer. He underwent a right lower lobectomy and mediastinal lymph node dissection. Histopathological evaluation confirmed squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). No lymph node involvement or distant metastasis was observed. Due to the early stage (Stage I), adjuvant chemotherapy was not administered, and the patient was followed up regularly by the oncology department.

Medical History: The patient had a history of Polycythemia Vera, Hypertension, and had ceased smoking five years prior.

Follow-Up and Metastasis: Routine follow-ups with thoracic and abdominal CT scans showed no signs of recurrence for over a year. However, in November 2023, a suspicious lesion was detected in the left kidney on abdominal CT. A percutaneous biopsy confirmed metastatic SCC. Consequently, left nephrectomy was performed in May 2024, and histopathology confirmed metastatic disease of pulmonary origin.

Current Status: The patient was reclassified as Stage IV and received systemic chemotherapy. As of the latest follow-up, there are no signs of active disease or further metastasis.

DISCUSSION

Although national cancer screening programs exist for several cancer types such as breast, cervical, and colorectal cancers, a national screening program for lung cancer has yet to be implemented in many countries, including ours. However, lung cancer remains the leading cause of cancer-related deaths worldwide, primarily due to late-stage diagnosis. One of the unique challenges in detecting lung cancer early is the paucity of pain receptors in pulmonary tissue, which allows tumors to grow silently without causing significant discomfort. The most prevalent early symptom -persistent coughing- is often overlooked by patients, especially among smokers, who commonly experience chronic cough due to smoking-related airway irritation. As a result, lung cancer is frequently diagnosed at an advanced stage when curative treatment is less likely to be effective. Evidence from large clinical trials has shown that low-dose computed tomography (LDCT) screening significantly reduces mortality from lung cancer among high-risk populations. Notably, the National Lung Screening Trial (NLST) in the United States demonstrated a 20% reduction in lung cancer-specific mortality with annual LDCT screening compared to chest X-ray among individuals aged 55–74 years with a smoking history of ≥ 30 pack-years (Aberle et al., 2011). Similarly, the NELSON trial conducted in Europe confirmed that LDCT screening in high-risk men and women led to a significant reduction in lung cancer mortality (de Koning et al., 2020; Mazzone et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

Given these findings, we strongly advocate for the implementation of a national lung cancer screening program targeting high-risk individuals in our country. Such an initiative would likely enable earlier detection, timely intervention, and a significant decrease in lung cancer-related morbidity and mortality. In addition, screening programs could facilitate earlier identification of other smoking-related conditions, including chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), further improving long-term outcomes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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